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Research Article

STUDY TO KNOW METABOLIC SYNDROME AMONG POSTMENOPAUSAL WOMEN AND EFFECTS OF VITAMIN D

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Abstract:

Background: Metabolic syndrome (MS) is a group of metabolic risk factors for cardiovascular diseases (CVD). Postmenopausal women may have an increased risk of MS and CVD. Vitamin-D (Vit-D) have an important role in the progression of CVD.

Aim: This study was conducted to assess the link between Vit-D and MS among postmenopausal women.

Study Design: A cross-sectional study was carried out; in the department of gynecology, Mayo Hospital Lahore from October 2019 to March 2020.

Materials and Methods: A total of 288 postmenopausal women were enrolled in the study Anthropometric measurements were measured using the standard procedure. Blood samples were collected and Vit-D levels of all participants were estimated. The study population was further grouped into three based on the Vit-D status as Vit-D deficient, Vit-D insufficient Vit-D normal group. Other parameters such as blood glucose, TC, TG, HDL, and LDL were measured and metabolic syndrome was identified.

Result: There was a significant difference in the prevalence of MS between the groups. The one way ANOVA between the groups showed a significant difference ($p \leq 0.05$) for the components of MS such as waist circumference, BP, FBS, HDL-C. The Triglycerides levels did not show a significant difference between the groups. The Person correlation test indicated a negative correlation between Vit-D and the components of MS except for HDL-C.

Conclusion: Vitamin-D deficiency was highly prevalent in menopausal women and serum Vit- D levels were significantly correlated with the prevalence of MS in postmenopausal women; this finding indicates that Vit-D could be an important factor for the development of MS and further CVD.

Keywords: Metabolic syndrome, Vitamin D, menopause, Cardiovascular risk.

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INTRODUCTION:

Metabolic syndrome (MS) is a group of disorders characterized by the presence of abdominal obesity, hypertension, dyslipidemia and hyperglycemia.¹ Metabolic syndrome is well-identified risk factors for CVD and type-2 diabetes mellitus (DM).² Recent studies have suggested that the number of people with MS is increasing in the developing countries like India due to the increased intake of a westernized diet with a sedentary lifestyle.³ The increased incidence of MS may directly contribute to the increased cardiovascular morbidity and mortality. Postmenopausal women may have the high incidence of cardiovascular disease (CVD) due to the hormonal changes after the menopause. Identifying the risk for CVD is significant because more than 90% of the women experience menopause for more than onethird of their total lifespan.⁴ Since menopause is a risk factor for CVD; it should be addressed as one of the most important issues faced by modern women. When women attain menopause, they should closely observe their overall health to prevent CVD. The hormonal changes after menopause are also believed to be a contributing factor for the development of MS at menopausal transition.⁵ This may increase the risk for CVD among postmenopausal women. Evidence from various studies has proven that suboptimal levels of Vitamin-D (Vit-D) are thought to influence risk for CVD by altering risk factors such as hypertension, dyslipidemia and other components of MS.^{6,7} The incidence of MS is known to increase after menopause; however, studies assessing the relationship between MS with serum levels of Vit-D in postmenopausal women are lacking.

MATERIALS AND METHODS:

A cross-sectional study was carried out; in the department of gynecology, Mayo Hospital Lahore from October 2019 to March 2020. Participants were excluded if they had not provided blood samples for biochemical analysis and had not completed the questionnaire regarding the demographic and anthropometric variables such as height, weight, waist circumference (WC) and blood pressure (BP) (systolic & diastolic blood pressure).

Variable Measurements:

Anthropometric measurements such as height weight and waist circumference were measured

using the standard procedure. Blood pressure was measured in the sitting position prior to blood collection to avoid BP fluctuations due to apprehension during the vein puncture. Total of 5 ml blood sample was collected after overnight fasting, serum was separated as per the standard protocol. Vit-D levels were estimated by Chemiluminescence Immunoassays (CLIA) and test population was further grouped into three based on the Vit-D status. 10 1. Group-1: Vit-D deficient group (< 20 ng/mL) 2. Group- 2: Vit-D insufficient group (20–29 ng/mL) 3. Group-3: Vit-D normal group (≥ 30 ng/mL). A fully automated analyzer (Mindray BS200) was used to analyze the cardiovascular biomarkers such as blood glucose, lipid profiles (TC, TG, HDL, and LDL). Metabolic syndrome was identified as per the National Cholesterol Education Program Adult Treatment Panel III (NCEP-ATP III).¹¹ Statistical Analysis The demographic data like age, height, body weight were analyzed by descriptive statistics. Chisquare test was used to differentiate the presence of MS between the groups. One way ANOVA was used to identify the difference in parameters like BMI, SBP, DBP, Total Cholesterol, HDL, LD, Triglycerides between the groups. The statistical analysis was conducted by using SPSS software (version 21.0).

RESULT:

The study was conducted to assess the prevalence of MS among the post-menopausal women. A total of 288 postmenopausal women were enrolled in the study. Vit-D levels were assessed and the population was grouped into group1, 2 and 3 according to the Vit-D status. The average age of the participants was 55.45, 57.50 and 59.63 for the group1, 2, and 3 respectively. This shows a comparable age difference of the subjects in three groups. The Chi-square test between the groups indicated that there is a significant difference in the prevalence of MS between the groups. Group-1 had a higher prevalence of MS compare to group-2 and 3. The one way ANOVA between the groups showed a significant difference ($p \leq 0.05$) for the components of MS such as waist circumference, BP, FBS, HDL-C. The Triglycerides levels did not show a significant difference between the groups (Table 1). The Person correlation test of Vit-D with components of MS such as waist circumference, FBS, BP, and TG is showing a negative correlation. Vit-D levels showed a positive correlation with HDL levels. This indicates that Vit-D plays an important role in the development Of MS.

Table 1: Comparison of the components of MS between three groups

Components of MS		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
BP DIA	Between Groups	594.713	2	297.357	3.027	.050*
	Within Groups	28096.000	286	98.238		
	Total	28690.713	288			
FBS	Between Groups	79674.961	2	39837.481	33.850	.000**
	Within Groups	336587.849	286	1176.881		
	Total	416262.810	288			
HDL	Between Groups	1972.862	2	986.431	29.533	.000**
	Within Groups	9552.730	286	33.401		
	Total	11525.592	288			
LDL	Between Groups	4177.338	2	2088.669	3.007	.035*
	Within Groups	198627.597	286	694.502		
	Total	202804.934	288			
TG	Between Groups	1812.253	2	906.126	.634	.531
	Within Groups	408531.075	286	1428.430		
	Total	410343.328	288			

Statistical test used: One Way Anova F test, ** p<0.01 Highly significant, *P<0.05 Significant

DISCUSSION:

In this cross sectional study, the prevalence of MS in postmenopausal women tended to decrease as serum levels of Vit-D increased, this association was statistically significant. A higher prevalence of MS has been reported in women, especially those aged more than 50 years, as compared with men.^{11,12} Another Indian study reported that the prevalence of MS increased after menopause.¹³ A study in the U.S. conducted by Park YW *et al*, demonstrated an increased risk of MS up to more than 20% among postmenopausal women.^{9,14} Moreover, a study that examined the prevalence of MS and its association with hyperinsulinemia in the urban Korean population concluded by Oh JY *et al* found that the prevalence of MS increased with increasing incidence of insulin resistance.¹⁵ However, to the best of our knowledge, this is the first study to reveal the effect of serum levels of Vit-D on MS among postmenopausal women. Several reports have demonstrated a significant inverse association between serum Vit-D levels and the prevalence of MS.¹⁶⁻¹⁸ Other studies, similar to ours, have observed an association between serum levels of Vit-D and MS and the results were at par with our findings.¹⁹ Several studies have conducted across the world and observed that VitD status can influence the progression of MS. In a

study conducted by Botella-Carretero JI *et al*, found that VitD status is associated with MS among the obese population in U.S.²⁰ Some of the major factors observed in our study are the considerable abnormalities in lipid profiles. In our study, the Vit-D deficient group had high LDL-C and reduced the HDL-C level. In several studies, it has found that the levels of LDL-C and TGs levels generally known to be increased in the postmenopausal stage as compared with premenopausal stage, and the cardio protective effects in females are known to be lost after menopause with a considerable fall in HDL-C levels. Our study pointed that elevated BP (both systolic and diastolic) and fasting blood sugar levels were significantly elevated and associated with Vit-D levels in postmenopausal women, these findings are at par with several other studies. Since it is a cross sectional study, the direct relationship between the variables of interest could not be determined and we could not consider parameters such as intensity of sunlight exposure, calcium supplementation, and Vit-D intake which could have influenced the Vit-D levels in the blood.

CONCLUSION:

The finding of this study indicates that Vit-D is an important factor for the development of MS in

postmenopausal women. Based on our findings, it is recommended to have a periodical cardiovascular health monitoring for the postmenopausal women with MS.

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